

A NARRATIVE ANALYSIS ON TRIPADVISOR REVIEWS OF GUEST SATISFACTION IN CONRAD MANILA AS A QUARANTINE FACILITY 2020-2021

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Abstract: The research paper utilized customer evaluation and feedback, particularly those found on TripAdvisor, the research discusses the satisfaction of prior quarantine guests of Conrad Hotel Manila. Researchers gathered the information for the study to determine the service quality that satisfied and dissatisfied the guests during their quarantine stay. The research gathered reviews from 2020–2021 in order to analyze and evaluate the following service quality variables including Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy. To determine the distributions of each review to the service quality variable, the researchers applied narrative analysis to narrate the reviews under each variable, while quantitative research is used to count the total number of reviews under each service quality. The results of the quantitative analysis show that the service quality attribute that satisfied the guests is the reliability variable for the reason that a significant number of previous quarantine guests indicated that Conrad hotel has well-trained staff and excellent food, this was a total of 84 out of 315 positive statements. On the other hand, the majority of the negative reviews are related to the tangible variable with a total of 7 out of 20 negative statements that dissatisfied the guests during their quarantine period.

Keywords: customer evaluation, service quality, Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, TripAdvisor.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Covid 19 pandemic has changed guest satisfaction standards, considering their safety against the virus which is a highly contagious respiratory disease that spreads through exposure to other infected people (Davahli, 2020). According to Aquino (2021), quarantine hotels play an important role in the pandemic as isolation and quarantine facilities. With this, hotels must improve health preparation and enforce proactive precautionary measures.

The study by Hussain & Kareem's (2020) stated that sanitation and health services are the most important considerations for guests and have become the standard of hotel services during the outbreak. The standards of guests to hotels in the new normal would affect what they desire from booking a hotel, customers desire to know that their health has been prioritized (Fexco, 2020). According to Kumar (2021), the main reasons that guests may be satisfied during the hotel quarantine stay may be seen in staff, service, room, cleanliness, fast booking, and the pandemic response of the hotel. Guest satisfaction is the major goal of hotels, and it is the foundation of achieving success as mentioned by Haur et al., (2017). With this being

said, there are guest standards that could be utilized as a guideline for delivering high-quality services and customer satisfaction (Wang et al., 2021). Hotel management that enhances customer satisfaction can build trust and maintain a positive image for the hotel. On the other hand, a business that disregards the satisfaction of its customers risks developing an unfavorable public image associated with the company. A guest's choice of hotel could be influenced by feedback from previous customer experiences. Furthermore, assessing feedback on customer satisfaction after the provided accommodation service is crucial in the hotel industry. Hotel managers can utilize customer feedback to make adjustments to their practices to increase service quality, this is by analyzing the guests' reviews of the service offered (Hussain & Kanna, 2019). In relation to that, online reviews would be a great platform for Conrad Hotel to evaluate its performance as a quarantine facility and have room for innovation.

Conrad Hotel is a 5-star hotel that is part of Hilton Hotels Corporation, it is an international hospitality corporation based in the United States that owns and operates a selection of hotels and resorts. Conrad Hilton created the company in May 1919, and Christopher J. Hilton is the current CEO. The hotel is located in Pasay and is 15 minutes away from Ninoy Aquino International Airport. According to the Official Website of Conrad Hotel Manila, the hotel is on top of the S Maison shopping district on the borders of Manila Bay, with convenient access to the Mall of Asia. The Conrad Hotel is a hotel converted into a Department of Tourism (DOT) accredited quarantine facility as a response to the pandemic and is on the list of Department of Health (DOH) and Bureau of Quarantine (BOQ) facilities suitable as Mandatory and Stringent quarantine facility; it allows the hotel to quarantine individuals arriving from high-risk countries based on the Bureau of Quarantine (2021).

The researchers chose Conrad Hotel Manila as the subject of the paper considering that it is certified as a five-star quarantine facility that provides a "patriotic service" during the pandemic to provide the best possible accommodation with a luxury mindset of prioritizing the health and safety of their guests. There are a few aspects the researchers took into consideration in choosing to analyze the customer satisfaction of Conrad Hotel as a quarantine facility, it includes the accessibility of the location and the accreditation the hotel holds. On the other hand, TripAdvisor will be the basis for the reviews of Conrad Hotel due to the reason that the hotel is subscribed to the platform. TripAdvisor is the biggest travel site around the world and serves as a guide for travelers to choose the best place for their preferred destination according to Sumarsono (2019). This adds up to the reason behind using the reviews found on TripAdvisor to analyze the customer satisfaction of the guests that quarantined in Conrad Hotel.

The general problem focuses on the TripAdvisor feedback of the previous quarantine guests in Conrad Hotel Manila from March 2020 - December 2021. Through the data gathering, the researchers noticed that Conrad Hotel had a lot of positive reviews regarding their quarantine services, although there were still a few negative feedbacks. Reviews have the ability to impact customer decisions as well as increase a company's reputation. According to Kats (2019), customer trust may be gained through reviews, and they inspire customers to connect with the business. Overall, it may also result in improvements to their services that will fully satisfy their guests during their quarantine period.

The researchers gathered the reviews to identify the customer satisfaction of the guests during their quarantine period. Specifically, the research paper will answer the question:

- What is the service quality that satisfied the quarantine guests of Conrad Hotel Manila during their stay?

The significance of the study will benefit the hotel and its employees to improve the service quality provided as a quarantine facility. This will also help them to maintain their promised service as a 5-star Hotel and build loyalty toward potential guests. The study will also benefit other quarantine hotels to enhance their service quality as a quarantine facility. The research will benefit the Philippines to attract tourists from other countries to visit. The data acquired will help visitors feel assured that the Philippines has safe, luxurious, and comfortable quarantine facilities available. This is also beneficial for future researchers and the University, wherein the data gathered can provide knowledge for individuals and be used as a reference in writing a related study.

The researchers selected this topic considering that it is unique and relevant to today's situation. The research is a current topic wherein there has been no specific study conducted that evaluates customer satisfaction regarding the service quality of hotel quarantine facilities in the Philippines. The study allows the researchers to comprehend if the guests are satisfied or dissatisfied with the quality of service the hotel performs. By analyzing the feedback from TripAdvisor reviews, the possible negative comments will help the hotel improve the guests' overall experience by enhancing the quality of service provided. Quarantine is a safety requirement for arriving individuals in the Philippines, as a result, the research topic is a significant factor in the COVID-19 situation.

The research is limited to reviews from March 2020- December 2021 on TripAdvisor by previous guests who were quarantined in Conrad Hotel. The researchers chose to focus on reviews from March 2020-December 2021, the year that the hotel quarantine facility was established and regulated. The researchers started conducting the study in October 2021 and it was completed by the end of the semester.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The research method used is a conceptual framework adapted from the SERVQUAL Model of Parasuraman et al. as cited in the study by Kalotra & Sharma entitled “Measuring Service Quality using SERVQUAL in Hospitality Industry” as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. SERVQUAL Model

According to Kalotra and Sharma (2017), measuring service quality using SERVQUAL in the hospitality industry evaluates the customer satisfaction that they experience based on the five variables of the model. Guest experience is used to measure hotel guest satisfaction, according to Chan et al., (2021). A set of factors, such as staff service quality, room quality, amenities, value, and security, may influence satisfaction. The SERVQUAL model consists of 5 variables, this includes tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. According to Ramya, N. (2019) tangibles, focus on how the physical attributes of the hotel can satisfy the guests. Assurance is classified as the employee’s knowledge, civility, and the firm’s capacity to inspire trust and confidence in its consumers. The ability to deliver the promised service consistently and precisely is characterized by reliability. Responsiveness is the willingness of the employees to help the guests and the attitude they portray when handling problems. Empathy is described as the caring; personalized attention offered to customers, implying that the guests are special and unique to the company. As a result, the application of the SERVQUAL model is the most suitable for the purpose of the study, it is to measure the hotel guest satisfaction of Conrad Hotel through the TripAdvisor reviews of the service delivered to previous guests and be able to analyze every aspect of satisfaction based on the 5 variables of the model.

The researchers used the TripAdvisor reviews of the previous guests that underwent quarantine in Conrad Hotel from March 2020 – December 2021. The data collected is analyzed and distributed to the category it correlates with.

3. RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

Researchers want to understand how guests evaluate service satisfaction throughout their time in a quarantine hotel (Wang et al., 2021). As mentioned by Pazir (2019), customer satisfaction can be defined as a hotel's ability to meet a guest's wants and desires. As a result, hotels must continually meet the requirements and needs of the customers. Pazir’s statement contributes to the study by providing knowledge on service quality that influences the satisfaction of hotel guests. Schimanovich (2021) indicated that to meet the demands of the guests, the industry had to implement new standards. Hotels must adapt to safety measures to compete in the market, considering that guests will have a sense of security when staying at the hotel. A hotel that stands out is one that can address both expressed and unexpressed consumer wants. Understanding who the customer is, predicting what their requirements are likely to be, and then creating an environment that meets and exceeds those demands are the first steps in providing excellent customer satisfaction (Sandoval, 2019). According to Tan (2019), to achieve customer satisfaction, it is necessary to understand and anticipate the demands of consumers and discover ways to meet those needs. The relevance to this study is that the researchers want to analyze the customer satisfaction of the previous guests of Conrad Hotel as a quarantine facility. It focuses on the different variables of the SERVQUAL model and how it is able to satisfy the guests.

A critique revealed that there is a gap in the SERVQUAL model that is adapted to the framework of the study, it focuses on the discrepancies between consumer expectations and the service provider's assessment of customer demands, according to Jonkisz, et al. (2021). The difference between what the customer anticipates and what the individual receives is a gap, considering that it results in a comparison of the customer expectation and the service quality experienced. As a result, the researchers utilized a conceptual framework adapted from the SERVQUAL model to eliminate the gap as stated by Jonkisz. To differentiate the SERVQUAL model from the adapted model in the study, the researchers did not include the expected service of the SERVQUAL model in the conceptual framework. The researchers focused on the 5 variables from the model to analyze the service quality of the guest experience.

A similar study entitled "*Understanding the perceived satisfaction and revisiting intentions of lodgers in a restricted service scenario: evidence from the hotel industry in quarantine*" by Wang et al, (2021) applied the same framework, which is the SERVQUAL model. Although, there is a difference in the adaptation of the SERVQUAL model. In the study of Wang et al., (2021), the revisit intentions of the lodgers are included in the framework, while this is not found in the model used in this study. According to Ervina et al., (2021), service is linked to satisfaction wherein the fundamental to tourism marketing strategy is satisfaction as a marketing tool. There was a shift in consumer orientation, health, and cleanliness aspects during the pandemic, and it became a consideration for staying guests when choosing a hotel, this statement agrees with the concept written in our study. The textual data from the reviews of TripAdvisor is the only data used in our study, on the other hand, the study from Nilashi et al., (2021) applied the neuro-fuzzy technique which utilizes both the numerical ratings and the variables derived from the textual data as well.

A study that contrasts a hotel as a quarantine facility stated that converting hotels for quarantine is less efficient than dedicated facilities due to inadequate ventilation and shared rooms by Grout et al., (2021). The research stated that there has been a total of 16 cases of contamination for quarantine hotels based in Australia and New Zealand. An article by Jazeera (2021) stated that a quarantine hotel in Victoria, Australia had an outbreak due to a violation of the procedures. On the other hand, there has been a development in the service of hotel quarantines in Australia. According to an interview with Hyde (2021), the service quality of the quarantine hotels has been improved and concluded that the country needs to keep the quarantine system and facilities. As stated by Visontay (2021), Australia improved its program by minimizing transmission from surfaces and hotel equipment, strict room isolation, workers wearing protective gear, and meals being scheduled to avoid contact with guests. The research relates to the study, considering that proper implementation is important for guests' during the pandemic and their safety is a source of customer satisfaction. Kumar (2021) analyzed that the main reason that guests may be satisfied during the hotel quarantine may be seen in staff, service, room, cleanliness, slow booking, and the pandemic response of the hotel. An article entitled "Poblacion Girl' faces criminal raps for breaking hotel quarantine rules" from manilastandard.net indicated that a woman who arrived from the United States named Gwyneth Anne Chua violated the mandatory COVID-19 quarantine rules, which led to infecting 15 of her companions during the night they partied and several other people in the bar. The prosecutor's office also filed charges against other Berjaya Hotel employees for helping her leave the quarantine facility. This is a result of a quarantine hotel not implementing strict observance of the regulations. It shows that choosing a quarantine facility that implements strict protocols is important for arriving guests to assure their safety against the virus.

A traveler in a hotel quarantine facility tested positive, and findings show that it infected another traveler on the same floor through the contamination in the hotel corridor according to Fox (2021). A journal about Emerging Infectious Diseases shows that the main reason is airborne transmission in the hallway. Some researchers also prove that Coronavirus can spread through tiny particles called aerosols and pass on to people when they inhale it. The World Health Organization (2020) mentioned that linens must be washed with the local public health regulations, this should be cleaned with hot water that is around 60-90 Celsius and laundry detergent. The surfaces should be cleaned and disinfected regularly to limit the risk of COVID-19 contamination. In addition to that, ventilation is a key factor for quarantine hotels. As a preventive procedure, cleaning and sanitation should be enforced in common places. On the other hand, the analysis of Tawfiq (2020), demonstrated that hotels exerted a lot of effort to convert into a quarantine facility, with this, hotels were fully prepared to contain the possible contact with the virus. The study stated that 23 out of the 1,928 mandatory quarantine guests tested positive and was immediately resolved. It is visible from the study that with proper implementations, hotel quarantine facilities can lower the rate of COVID-19-positive cases.

The effect of COVID-19 contains numerous opportunities for those who can comply with the customer behavioral change, due to guest enjoyment being the cornerstone to long-term growth and is a vital aspect of any hotel's operations. In the new normal, hotel customers' will influence their desire to stay in a hotel depending on the health standards as studied by Fexco

(2020). As mentioned by Ervina, et al. (2021), One of the survival measures of hotels in the face of the Covid-19 outbreak is to implement health protocols. With this, the research has concluded that a hotel's preparedness has an essential role in the hospitality industry. They should have the ability to provide comfort and minimize the spread of the virus, these are the most important factors that guests consider when choosing a place to stay. As a result of the implementation, the guest feels assured and safe at the hotel. According to an article from hospitality net organization (2021), The biggest factor that influenced the customer's decision to choose the hotel is the cleanliness, this assures the customer that the hotel is “virus-free”, and the protocols are implemented. In fact, 83% of travelers prefer to stay at a hotel that promotes the hotel's safety precautions. Hospitality focuses on quality and customer satisfaction, in this regard, the hotels have improved their services to gain the trust of travelers and maintain guest satisfaction. These studies draw upon the factors that quarantine hotels must perform to lead to customer satisfaction due to the change in hotel standards during the COVID-19 outbreak.

Service attitude is the foundation when it comes to customer satisfaction. The customer service practices that highly satisfy the guest include hands-on staff, offering of guest’s needs, entertainment, tutorial on the hotel’s available equipment, amenities, and customer practices as studied by Galiza (2020). Good service quality results in customer satisfaction and will lead to positive feedback or reviews. Conrad Hotel had a lot of positive reviews in regard to their quarantine services although there were still a few negative reviews. With this, the researchers’ gap focuses on the negative feedback on TripAdvisor from March 2020- December 2021. The researchers are the first ones to tackle the reviews of TripAdvisor towards Conrad Hotel as a quarantine facility. The Researchers aim to identify if the previous guests were satisfied or dissatisfied by assessing the problems of Conrad Hotel as a quarantine facility and to improve the experience during the quarantine period. The researchers gathered the reviews on TripAdvisor to assess even the small improvements that the hotel can do to fully satisfy their guests. Online customer evaluations help determine the satisfaction of guests during the pandemic and can indicate the guests' preferences for hotel service according to Nilashi (2021).

4. METHODOLOGY

The Research Design used is quantitative, considering that the researchers based the data on the total number of gathered reviews from a credible travel website. The research is a Quantitative Narrative analysis, the researchers narrate and analyze the common statements found in each variable that pertains to the customer satisfaction of the guests. According to Allen M. (2017), narrative analysis is used by researchers to learn how research participants create content and narratives based on their own experiences. In narrative analysis, there is a second layer of interpretation. First, the participants in the study use narrative to describe their own experiences, then the researchers interpret the written experience of the participants.

Figure 2. Data analysis

The data analysis used in this study is an analytic approach; the researchers identified the meaning of the data review based on the conceptual framework, SERVQUAL model of Parasuraman et al. In this method, researchers collect quantitative data through systematic observations by using techniques like counting the number of reviews present during 2020 - 2021

on TripAdvisor. The data is decoded into statements, then it is grouped into the variable from the framework it correlates with through creating a table in Microsoft Excel. Afterward, the researchers count the total number of statements found in each grouped variable. Furthermore, the statements found in the grouped variables are analyzed while the researchers concentrate on the common feedback. In addition, the researchers draw conclusions from analyzed data. The data analyzed from the research will be validated by the thesis adviser.

The data collection of the research is based on TripAdvisor as this will help make the research more legitimate because this site is trusted when it comes to people's experiences of traveling based on TripAdvisor's Official Website (2019). TripAdvisor data includes customer reviews and the descriptive features of hotels, this will be retrieved for the purpose of this study. Hotel guests submitted a review based on their overall satisfaction with the service that they experienced. The reviews from March 2020 - December 2021 that focus on the quarantine experience with Conrad Hotel are a total of 75 reviews on TripAdvisor. The researchers chose the year 2020-2021 considering that this is the year quarantine facilities were established. The researchers are allowed to retrieve information from TripAdvisor as stated in the website's accessibility statements. As seen in the appendix, it states that "content posted to TripAdvisor is available publicly".

For the researchers' ethical considerations, the researchers did not utilize any questionnaires for the data collection. The research is non-output based wherein the analysis will not be followed by any projects or recommendations for Conrad Hotel. The researchers sent emails for 3 consecutive days to ask permission to include the hotel in the research paper and to analyze the customer satisfaction of quarantined guests through the TripAdvisor reviews posted. Although, the establishment did not give the researchers any response as shown in the appendix. Despite this, the researchers have decided to proceed with the research and abide by the establishment's moral rights.

5. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The researchers' results and analysis focused on the decoded statements from the TripAdvisor reviews given by previous quarantine guests of Conrad Hotel Manila from the year March 2020 - December 2021. There are a total of 75 participants that have submitted their reviews during that year. The researchers decoded 335 statements out of the 75 reviews, 315 of the statements correspond to positive statements while 20 are negative statements about the service of Conrad Hotel. Afterward, the researchers grouped the statements to the variable it correlated with. After a thorough analysis of the reviews on the website, the results shown below are how the quarantine guests of Conrad Hotel are satisfied or dissatisfied with the service provided to them.

There are a total of 315 positive statements that were retrieved from the 75 reviews:

- There are 68 statements corresponding to the "Tangible" variable
- There are 84 statements corresponding to the "Reliability" variable
- There are 48 statements corresponding to the "Empathy" variable
- There are 63 statements corresponding to the "Responsiveness" variable
- There are 52 statements corresponding to the "Assurance" variable

Positive Tangible

There are 68 statements that correspond to the tangible variable of the SERVQUAL model. The researchers analyzed the top 5 common statements found in the grouped variable and these are:

- *"Very comfortable I have a nice view of Manila Bay, it's nice to see the sunset every day during our stay of quarantine"*
- *"Room was clean"*
- *"A big spacious cozy room with automatic blinds and curtains. The light fixtures are amazing, make me feel and look good. I stayed in room 4100 which has a positive vibe and good ambiance. Bed comfort was unbeatable. They have a very clean and spacious bathroom and powder room as well."*
- *"The room was sanitized well"*
- *"The hotel is very easy to access to MOA and airport"*

The common statements that correspond to the tangible variable focus on the physical attributes of the hotel. The reviews posted by the quarantine guests commented on the cleanliness, the ambiance, the amenities, and the view of the room. These are the different aspects that provided comfort and satisfaction for the quarantine stay of the guests.

Positive Reliability

There are 84 statements that correspond to the reliability variable of the SERVQUAL model. The researchers analyzed the top 5 common statements found in the grouped variable and these are:

- *“The breakfast which was served to us was very good, a lot of varieties to choose from.”*
- *“All throughout my stay, they made the experience memorable”*
- *“Food was great, carefully prepared and each dish served was truly a gastronomic delight. There may be limitations to the services offered at this time due to the pandemic regulations and guidelines but the team at Conrad Hotel has compensated for all the gaps.”*
- *“An excellent and well-trained members”*
- *“Overall experience of @ Conrad during the mandatory quarantine for OFWs was extremely perfect. Safety protocols have been implemented accordingly. The period of the quarantine was absolutely delightful.”*

The common statements that correspond to the reliability variable focus on the hotel’s ability to perform the promised service accurately and dependably. The reviews posted by the quarantine guests commented that the hotel is able to follow the protocols accordingly while providing a memorable experience through well-trained employees and great food options. These are the different aspects that made the guests feel safe while being satisfied with the services offered.

Positive Empathy

There are 48 statements that correspond to the empathy variable of the SERVQUAL model. The researchers analyzed the top 5 common statements found in the grouped variable and these are:

- *“I felt so taken care of. They would even call and check on me if I need anything. They made sure I was happy. And tell you what, I was beyond happy.”*
- *“Hotel team were extremely welcoming, friendly”*
- *“Conrad Manila kept my spirits uplifted while in quarantine.”*
- *“The staff of the hotel from guards, receptionist, dining, housekeeping and all staff are polite and friendly.”*
- *“All the staff is so welcoming, compassionate, and heartwarming which is why Filipino People are so famous worldwide.”*

The common statements that correspond to the empathy variable focus on the positive feelings that the employees conveyed to the guests. The reviews posted by the quarantine guests commented on the satisfaction that they felt from the hospitable attitude of the employees.

Positive Responsiveness

There are 63 statements that correspond to the responsiveness variable of the SERVQUAL model. The researchers analyzed the top 5 common statements found in the grouped variable and these are:

- *“They were all very accommodating and looking after the welfare of the guests. In short, we're really satisfied with the excellent customer service.”*
- *“Everyone was very punctual with services requested and when promised to be given updates.”*
- *“The staff was very attentive and contacting them through the Hilton app seemed like the best method of communication (sometimes we called and no one would pick up after several minutes of ringing).”*
- *“The Conrad staff had provided me with everything I wanted & needed for my long stay. Even random late-night food craving calls were answered!”*
- *“Anything needed is a '0' away.”*

The common statements that correspond to the responsiveness variable focus on the willingness of the employees to be of service to the guests. The reviews posted by the quarantine guests commented on the attentiveness of the employees and the immediate response to the requests of the guests. These are the aspects that satisfied the needs and desires of the guests during their quarantine period.

Positive Assurance

There are 52 statements that correspond to the assurance variable of the SERVQUAL model. The researchers analyzed the top 5 common statements found in the grouped variable and these are:

- *“I really like how Hilton values their loyal members by giving the best perks available if possible. Makes staying with them worth it, especially their luxury brands.”*
- *“I will definitely recommend this hotel to all my friends both local and international.”*
- *“Disclosure - my wife and I are both Hilton Honors Lifetime Diamond members.”*
- *“One of the best hotels in the Philippines for sure!”*
- *“We were assured that they would improve their level of service and they did make good on their promise.”*

The common statements that correspond to the assurance variable focus on the experience provided to the guests, that led to the trust in Conrad hotel as a quarantine facility. The reviews posted by the quarantine guests commented that they were satisfied and secured with the quarantine stay. As a result, the guests would recommend the hotel to others and would definitely come back.

While there are a total of 20 negative statements that were retrieved from the 75 reviews:

- There are 7 statements corresponding to the “Tangible” variable
- There are 6 statements corresponding to the “Reliability” variable
- There are 0 statements corresponding to the “Empathy” variable
- There are 4 statements corresponding to the “Responsiveness” variable
- There are 3 statements corresponding to the “Assurance” variable

Negative Tangible

There are 7 statements that correspond to the tangible variable of the SERVQUAL model and these are:

- *“The other small inconvenience was that the bedroom was way too cold while the living room was too warm which eventually led us to request engineering. Took them some time to calibrate the air conditioning settings properly and we wouldn't have raised this concern under normal circumstances but since we were confined in that space for an extended period we definitely wanted to make sure we were comfortable”*
- *“I was there for 6 days during my quarantine upon arrival from Los Angeles but no one clean my rm the whole time. Trash was also not picked up. “*
- *“Other than a few room issues I had a great experience.”*
- *“My only real issue was the blinds in the room were screwed shut so getting natural daylight was hard making my sleep schedule hard to pin down. The real issue with me was there was an amount of fungus growing on the ceiling near the bathroom slider door. That was off-putting with the cleanliness and the floor definitely needed to be vacuumed and steam cleaned as I found quite a lot of other person's hair around”*
- *“A pungent smell emanates from its ventilation. Better change that disinfectant chemical you are probably using Hilton.”*
- *“Just a simple suggestion, take off those chairs on floors not intended for quarantine.”*
- *“TV is old (with no Apps such as Netflix) so we didn't bother using it.”*

The negative statements that correspond to the tangible variable discuss the problems that occurred in the guest's room during the quarantine stay. This includes room odor, ventilation problems, uncleanliness, and furniture issues. These are the aspects that dissatisfied the guest's comfortability during their stay.

Negative Reliability

There are 6 statements that correspond to the reliability variable of the SERVQUAL model and these are:

- *"They messed up a few of our orders which became frustrating especially since we had jetlagged, hungry kids to feed."*
- *"Food is terrible too. Very small portion even though I signed in for buffet breakfast. Food is on the salty side."*
- *"With a few shortcomings in the kitchen and housekeeping. Bad tasteless food during room service."*
- *"Overall it's ok. The hotel price is good and the food was also good except the fruit platter was not checked before it was sent to my room."*
- *"A few times minor catering requests were missed such as extra brewed coffee and salt n pepper shakers."*
- *"Power interruption, an outage for 3-4 hrs in the early morning. And to think I'm an insomniac. This is uncharacteristic of a 5-star deluxe property."*

The negative statements that correspond to the reliability variable discuss the shortcomings of the hotel's services to the guests. This includes food conflicts such as messed-up orders and tasteless food. Another conflict is the power interruption that lasted 3-4 hours. These are the aspects of service that disappointed the guests, for the reason that it is not the quality of service that the guests expected from a 5-star hotel.

Negative Responsiveness

There are 4 statements that correspond to the responsiveness variable of the SERVQUAL model, and these are:

- *"The in-room dining service during the first few days was quite slow"*
- *"The long check-in process, and the one-hour wait when the room is not yet ready by 5 pm that i arrived."*
- *"We booked a Diplomatic Suite directly from Hilton's website. We arrived late (check-in time is 3 pm) around 4:20 pm and the front desk told us to wait a little more either at the lobby or just stay at the executive lounge because the "Supervisor" will do an "expedite" check with our room. Us thinking okay must be a quick check so let's go to the lounge first. By 4:30 pm we were at the lounge and were asked what we want to drink. Mind you there were not many people in the lounge at that time but it took them 20 minutes for the drinks to be served. If we didn't ask it from the server, for sure they have forgotten about it. First time experiencing that kind of service from a hotel lounge and I never forget that."*
- *"By 4:58 pm I approached the person manning the lounge where our room key card was, I was told again that word "expedite" check (it's like they're programmed to say that word) and just stay put for another 15 minutes! Conrad Manila, is that your best-expedited check of a room? 45minutes? We already checked in late and you guys have the audacity to tell me that the room will still be checked THAT LONG?"*

The negative statements that correspond to the responsiveness variable discuss the slow or delayed service that the guests received. This includes a long check-in process, slow room service, and prolonged service. These are the aspects that dissatisfied the guest's experience in regard to the service provided by Conrad employees.

Negative Assurance

There are 3 statements that correspond to the assurance variable of the SERVQUAL model, and these are:

- *"One of the most expensive hotels in Manila so my expectation is high."*
- *"For now, I am deviating from the usual 5-star I usually give this hotel."*
- *"Will we go back? Big No. We don't wanna get frustrated again."*

The negative statements that correspond to the assurance variable discuss the failure of Conrad to guarantee trust and confidence to the quarantine guests. The statements show that the guests are dissatisfied and have no revisit intentions due to the reason that the expectations were not met.

Negative Empathy

There are 0 statements that correspond to the empathy variable of the SERVQUAL model. This shows that the guests have no complaints or issues with the empathy that the employees show to guests.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

For the conclusion of this study, there are a total of 75 participants that have submitted their reviews on TripAdvisor from the year 2020-2021. The respondents gave different evaluations of their quarantine stay, some gave positive reviews, and a few gave negative reviews. Both the year 2020 and 2021 have positive feedback while most of the negative feedback is in the year 2021. In one review by Clarice Anne (2021), a previous guest of Conrad Manila commented, *"I like the hotel accommodation, very comfortable, clean, and safe and well hospitable staff. The receptionists I keep calling because my documents were still not in my hand but fortunately they deliver straight on my room. The food they deliver is delicious and safe. This good for quarantine accommodation also. As my company choose this 5-star hotel for my rate. The hotel is very easy to access to MOA and airport. Thanks for the food."* Conrad Manila is a well-known 5-star hotel and is a Department of Health (DOH) and Bureau of Quarantine (BOQ) accredited quarantine facility. Most of the guests of Conrad Hotel are individuals arriving from other countries that undergo mandatory quarantine.

The purpose of studying the satisfaction of previous quarantine guests is to improve the quality of service and to give future guests a better quarantine experience. As a result, the researchers analyzed the performance of the hotel and the results are outstanding, this means that Conrad Hotel is true to its promise of providing quality service to its guests. The researchers can conclude that Conrad Hotel can improve its reputation through its reviews and comments if it retains the majority of its service quality. However, given the small number of unfavorable evaluations, there are a few factors the hotel needs to consider to totally improve the feedback it has received. *"I stayed here for the mandated quarantine period prior to heading to SBMA. Other than a few room issues I had a great experience. My only real issue was the blinds in the room were screwed shut so getting natural daylight was hard making my sleep schedule hard to pin down. The real issue with me was there was an amount of fungus growing on the ceiling near the bathroom slider door. That was off-putting with the cleanliness and the floor definitely needed to be vacuumed and steam cleaned as I found quite a lot of other person's hair around (Zadam 2021)."* The main implication obtained from this study is the satisfaction of guests in Conrad Hotel Manila, making the guests feel comfortable, safe, and satisfied throughout their stay. The study will benefit not just Conrad Hotel but other quarantine facilities in the industry, as reviews and feedback from previous customers are really important to a business, it's a method to know the performance of the business. Analyzing the few negative reviews will help the hotel enhance and develop its services. According to the feedback, a few room concerns, cleaning issues, ventilation problems, poor food quality, and a lengthy check-in process are considered as the primary issues with Conrad Manila.

The research has obtained that the service quality that has dissatisfied the guests is the tangible variable due to the reason that the majority of the negative reviews in the results are related to the tangible variable with a total of 7 out of the 20 statements, this focuses on the physical attributes such as unpleasant room odors, ventilation concerns, cleanliness, and furniture problems. As stated by Archie B. (2021), *"I was there for 6 days during my quarantine upon arrival from Los Angeles but no one clean my rm the whole time. Trash was also not picked up."* These are the areas where Conrad Hotel Manila has to improve, accordingly. The researchers concluded that as a quarantine facility, the guests prioritize the cleanliness and sanitation of the hotel and the reliability of the hotel to perform its promises including the safety against the virus. As seen from the results of the research, the guests noticed the negative aspects of the physical attributes of the hotel for the reason that quarantine is a lengthy stay in which comfortability and cleanliness are essential factors that they consider. As a result, Conrad Hotel Manila needs to focus on improving the physical attributes of the quarantine rooms to assure that every quarantine guest will be satisfied during their stay.

On the other hand, the service quality that satisfied the guests is the reliability variable considering that the majority of the positive reviews are related to the reliability variable with a total of 84 out of 315 statements, indicating that the remarkable experiences provided by Conrad Hotel's well-trained staff and excellent food were the main reasons for the satisfaction of a substantial number of previous quarantine guests. This shows that a large number of the guests consider the hotel's capacity to deliver the promised service accurately and dependably. According to Jennifer M. (2021), *"Food was great, carefully prepared and each dish served was truly a gastronomic delight. There may be limitations to the services offered at this time due to the pandemic regulations and guidelines but the team at Conrad Hotel has compensated for all the gaps."* The researchers concluded that the hotel's reliability is recommended by a lot of their previous guests because they state that they can rely on the quarantine services offered by Conrad Hotel Manila. However, they should maintain the performance and continue to improve to provide the best quality of service to assure the satisfaction of the guests.

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